

Article

Interpretable Vision Transformers in Monocular Depth Estimation via SVDA

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Abstract

Monocular depth estimation is a central problem in computer vision with applications in robotics, augmented reality, and autonomous driving, yet the self-attention mechanisms used by modern Transformer architectures remain opaque. In this work, we integrate SVD-Inspired Attention (SVDA) into the Dense Prediction Transformer (DPT), introducing a spectrally structured attention formulation for dense prediction that decouples directional alignment from spectral modulation through a learnable diagonal matrix embedded in normalized query–key interactions. Experiments on KITTI and NYU-v2 show that SVDA preserves competitive predictive performance while enabling intrinsic interpretability: on KITTI, AbsRel improves from 0.058 to 0.056 and δ_1 from 0.976 to 0.979, while on NYU-v2, AbsRel improves from 0.133 to 0.124 and δ_1 from 0.865 to 0.872. This is achieved with only 0.01% additional parameters, at the cost of a measurable runtime overhead associated with the added normalization and spectral modulation. More importantly, SVDA enables six spectral indicators that quantify entropy, rank, sparsity, alignment, selectivity, and robustness, revealing consistent cross-dataset and depth-wise patterns in how attention organizes during training. These properties make the model easier to inspect and better suited to applications where transparency and reliability are important, such as robotics and autonomous navigation.

Keywords: monocular; depth; transformers; self-attention; SVD; interpretability**MSC:** 68T45; 68U10; 68T07

1. Introduction

Monocular depth estimation, the task of predicting per-pixel depth from a single RGB image, is an inherently ill-posed problem with wide-ranging applications in autonomous navigation, augmented reality, and 3D scene reconstruction [1]. Recent advances in vision Transformers, such as the Dense Prediction Transformer (DPT), have demonstrated strong performance in this domain by leveraging global self-attention and multi-scale feature fusion [2]. However, despite their empirical success, these models remain largely opaque, with attention mechanisms that are difficult to interpret and lacking in geometric or semantic structure [3–6].

While dense prediction tasks such as depth estimation require fine-grained spatial reasoning, current Transformer-based models often yield attention maps that are dense and uninterpretable. This opacity limits our ability to understand the model’s internal representations and compromises trust in high-stakes applications such as robotics, autonomous

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driving, and scientific measurement [7]. Prior work in image classification has shown that standard attention maps may fail to reflect semantically meaningful interactions [4], and similar concerns apply to dense regression tasks [7]. *Addressing this challenge calls for attention mechanisms that promote interpretability, structured behavior, and semantic alignment with scene geometry.*

In this work, we integrate the SVD-Inspired Attention (SVDA) mechanism [8] into the DPT framework to enhance interpretability in monocular depth estimation. SVDA replaces the standard dot-product formulation with a spectral attention design, consisting of row-wise normalized query/key projections and a learnable diagonal spectral modulation matrix Σ . Inspired by Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), this structure decouples directional attention from spectral importance, a property especially beneficial for depth prediction, where spatial continuity and semantic coherence are critical. *This formulation produces attention maps that are intrinsically interpretable, requiring only minimal architectural change while preserving competitive predictive accuracy.* In addition to enhancing attention structure, SVDA unlocks a suite of spectral indicators that expose the inner mechanics of attention layers. These indicators establish a coherent diagnostic framework for probing interpretability, directional alignment, and information flow across layers and heads.

The research gap addressed in this paper lies between two dominant lines of prior work. On the one hand, post hoc interpretability methods attempt to explain already-trained Transformer models through saliency, attribution, or visualization, but they do not modify the attention operator itself and therefore do not make attention intrinsically structured or directly diagnosable during training. On the other hand, performance-driven monocular depth estimation architectures improve accuracy, efficiency, or multi-scale fusion, yet they typically leave the internal organization of attention opaque. Our work targets this missing middle ground by introducing an intrinsic, spectrally structured attention mechanism within DPT, so that interpretability arises from the formulation of attention itself rather than from external explanatory tools applied after inference.

This work explores the integration of SVDA into the DPT architecture for monocular depth estimation, with a focus on enhancing interpretability through spectral structure. We conduct experiments on two diverse datasets, KITTI and NYU-v2, and evaluate interpretability using six spectral indicators—spectral entropy, effective rank, angular alignment, selectivity index, spectral sparsity, and perturbation robustness—that quantify structure and concentration in the attention maps. More specifically, the paper is guided by two research questions: (RQ1) "Can a spectrally structured attention mechanism be introduced into DPT without compromising predictive performance in monocular depth estimation?" and (RQ2) "Does the resulting formulation expose stable and meaningful attention diagnostics that remain inaccessible in standard dot-product attention?"

Our key contributions are:

- **Methodological contribution:** we adapt SVDA to the Dense Prediction Transformer (DPT), replacing standard dot-product attention with a spectrally structured formulation based on normalized query/key projections and a learnable diagonal modulation matrix for monocular depth estimation.
- **Empirical contribution:** we show on KITTI and NYU-v2 that the proposed integration preserves competitive predictive accuracy while enabling intrinsic interpretability with minimal parameter overhead.
- **Analytical contribution:** we demonstrate that the resulting spectral indicators provide a practical diagnostic framework for examining attention dynamics, sparsity, alignment, and robustness across layers and training epochs in monocular depth estimation.

This approach bridges spectral theory with practical vision architectures, enabling interpretable Transformer behavior in spatially continuous tasks such as depth estimation.

2. Related Work

Monocular Depth Estimation (MDE) has advanced rapidly with deep learning, evolving from early convolutional models [9,10] to more recent Transformer-based architectures. The Dense Prediction Transformer (DPT) [2] introduced a ViT-style encoder–decoder framework capable of modeling long-range dependencies and multi-scale semantics, setting a new benchmark in dense regression. AdaBins [11] extended this line by discretizing depth into adaptive bins, significantly improving resolution and consistency.

Several follow-up works apply Transformers to MDE using architectural innovations or self-supervision. MonoViT [12] integrates ViTs into a self-supervised framework, while Depthformer [13] combines multi-scale attention with depth-aware fusion strategies. CATNet [14] and PCTDepth [15] explore hybrid CNN–Transformer decoders to balance local detail with global context. These methods improve predictive quality or architectural efficiency, but their design emphasis remains performance-oriented: attention is treated primarily as a computational mechanism for feature interaction, not as an intrinsically interpretable object. As a result, they provide limited visibility into how attention organizes across layers, which latent directions dominate, or how internal attention structure evolves during training.

Interpretability of attention mechanisms remains a fundamental concern in Transformer models, particularly for dense prediction tasks. While attention is often treated as an explanatory tool, foundational studies have cautioned against over-reliance on raw attention maps for interpretability [4,16]. More recently, Wu et al. [17] further examined the faithfulness of Vision Transformer explanations, reinforcing the need for interpretability frameworks that go beyond visually plausible but potentially incomplete attention-based accounts. In the vision domain, Chefer et al. [5] extend attention-based explanation with attribution propagation, and Raghu et al. [6] analyze how attention evolves across layers; however, these methods remain fundamentally post hoc, as they explain model behavior after training rather than redesigning attention to be interpretable by construction. Beyond classification, You et al. [18] introduced a unit-level approach for monocular depth estimation that assigns semantic roles to hidden activations. While valuable, that formulation operates at the neuron level and does not characterize the spectral organization of attention across heads and layers. Gipiškis et al. [19] surveyed explainable AI methods in segmentation, emphasizing attribution maps and visual explanation techniques to guide model design and compression; however, these remain largely prescriptive overlays on otherwise opaque architectures. More recently, Cirillo et al. [20] assessed attribution methods in monocular depth estimation through a fidelity-oriented evaluation framework. Their contribution is important for post hoc explanation assessment, but it still does not provide an intrinsic reformulation of attention itself. In contrast, SVDA does not attach explanations to a conventional attention block after inference; it restructures the attention mechanism so that interpretability emerges from normalized directional interactions and explicit spectral modulation during training and analysis.

Recent works introduce geometric or structural priors into ViT architectures to improve depth estimation. Ruhkamp et al. [21] propose spatial–temporal attention modules informed by geometric constraints to enhance consistency. TinyDepth [22] and METER [23] inject inductive biases via lightweight attention decoders, while CATNet [14] and PCTDepth [15] combine local convolutional features with global Transformer heads for hybrid attention. These approaches show that structural bias can improve depth estimation, yet the imposed structure is primarily architectural or geometric. It does not decompose attention

into interpretable spectral components, nor does it provide explicit indicators for examining how attention concentration, sparsity, or alignment evolve within the model.

Although these methods incorporate structural biases—such as local/global fusion or convolutional regularization—*none apply spectral analysis or principled decomposition to inform or constrain the attention mechanism itself*. They optimize architectural design but do not address the interpretability or internal organization of attention maps.

Spectral decompositions, such as low-rank or kernel approximations for efficient inference [24], have been explored primarily for scalability rather than interpretability. Such methods reduce computational cost, but they do not expose a diagnostic spectral parameterization of attention that can be inspected head-wise and layer-wise during training. To the best of our knowledge, the original SVDA formulation [8] is the first work in our line of research to explicitly separate directional similarity from learned spectral weighting within attention itself, thereby turning spectral structure into an interpretable property of the operator rather than an approximation device.

In this work, we extend SVDA to the domain of monocular depth estimation. Unlike prior MDE models that rely on architectural heuristics or fusion strategies, and unlike post hoc explanation methods that operate outside the attention operator, SVDA embeds spectral structure directly into the attention computation. What is missing in prior work is precisely this combination of properties: an intrinsic attention reformulation, explicit spectral control, and a built-in diagnostic toolkit that quantifies entropy, rank, sparsity, alignment, selectivity, and robustness within a dense prediction Transformer. This positioning is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Positioning of representative prior works relative to the proposed SVDA-based formulation.

Representative Method(s)	Method Type	Interpretability	Main Limitation Relative to SVDA
DPT [2], AdaBins [11], MonoViT [12], Depthformer [13]	Performance-driven MDE	None/implicit	Improve depth quality, but do not make attention intrinsically interpretable or diagnostically structured.
CATNet [14], PCTDepth [15], ME-TER [23], TinyDepth [22]	Hybrid/structurally biased MDE	Implicit architectural bias	Introduce useful inductive biases, but do not provide spectral decomposition or head-wise/layer-wise interpretability indicators.
Chefer et al. [5], Raghu et al. [6], Cirillo et al. [20]	Post hoc explanation/analysis	Post hoc	Explain or evaluate model behavior after training, but do not reformulate the attention operator itself.
You et al. [18]	Interpretable MDE representation learning	Intrinsic (unit level)	Assign semantic roles to hidden activations, but do not model attention through spectral structure across heads and layers.
SVDA in DPT (ours)	Intrinsic attention reformulation	Intrinsic	Combines normalized directional attention, explicit spectral modulation, and a diagnostic toolkit for attention structure.

3. SVDA in Monocular Depth Estimation

SVDA imposes a structured decomposition on the attention mechanism by separating directional encoding from spectral modulation. Drawing inspiration from the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), it modifies conventional dot-product attention by applying ℓ_2 -normalized query and key projections together with a learnable, diagonal spectral matrix Σ unique to each attention head. The core SVDA attention is defined as follows. Let $Q, K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_k}$ be row-wise ℓ_2 -normalized projections (i.e., each row Q_i, K_j satisfies

$\|Q_i\|_2 = \|K_j\|_2 = 1$), and let $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{d_k \times d_k}$ be a learned diagonal matrix. Define the attention matrix as:

$$A = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{Q\Sigma K^\top}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $Q, K \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times d_k}$ denote the query and key matrices, normalized row-wise, and $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{d_k \times d_k}$ is a trainable diagonal matrix that adjusts the contribution of each latent dimension. This structure mirrors the SVD-inspired decomposition of attention into directional and spectral terms, facilitating interpretable and structured attention maps, subject to subsequent softmax normalization and head-wise processing.

The two main design choices in SVDA follow the original theoretical formulation in [8]. First, row-wise ℓ_2 normalization is applied to Q and K so that attention scores depend on directional alignment rather than vector magnitude. This yields a cosine-like similarity structure, stabilizes the geometry of the attention interaction, and makes the resulting scores easier to interpret in terms of angular relationships between tokens. In addition, consistent with the motivating SVD decomposition, where the singular-value matrix is diagonal, spectral modulation is implemented through a diagonal matrix Σ . This allows dimension-wise reweighting within the attention interaction, preserves a direct spectral interpretation of the learned modulation, and keeps the additional parameter cost minimal.

Our implementation closely follows the embedding pipeline of the original DPT architecture [2] for direct comparison. The image is first split into non-overlapping $P \times P$ patches, flattened into vectors, and passed through a learned linear projection to generate patch embeddings. Fixed-length learnable positional embeddings are added to patch tokens to maintain spatial order. These token sequences are then processed by a ViT encoder. The only departure from the baseline DPT model is the replacement of the self-attention mechanism with SVDA, as described in Eq.1 and detailed in [8].

To make the integration procedure explicit, Algorithm 1 summarizes how SVDA replaces the standard dot-product attention operator inside a DPT Transformer encoder block during the forward pass. The surrounding DPT scaffold remains unchanged; only the attention score computation is replaced by the SVDA formulation.

All models were trained from scratch in PyTorch for 100 epochs. We did not use pretrained or fine-tuned baselines, because our goal is not to maximize accuracy, but to isolate the effect of replacing dot-product attention with SVDA on (i) accuracy retention and (ii) measurable attention structure using the proposed indicators. Figure 1 summarizes the SVDA modification relative to standard attention.

From a computational perspective, SVDA preserves the dominant asymptotic complexity of standard attention. For a single head with n tokens and head dimension d_k , the main score and value products remain quadratic in the token count, i.e., $\mathcal{O}(n^2 d_k)$, as in conventional dot-product attention. Relative to the baseline, SVDA adds row-wise normalization of Q and K and diagonal spectral modulation via $Q\Sigma$, each of cost $\mathcal{O}(n d_k)$ per head, while the orthogonality regularization used during training introduces an additional $\mathcal{O}(d_k^2)$ term per head [8]. Therefore, the theoretical complexity class remains unchanged, and the observed runtime overhead should be interpreted primarily as a constant-factor cost associated with the added normalization, spectral modulation, and regularization operations rather than as a change in the dominant scaling behavior.

As defined in the original publication of SVDA, the interpretability indicators to be also used here include:

- Spectral Entropy $\mathcal{H}_\Sigma = -\sum p_i \log p_i$: Information indicator that captures focus/disorder in latent dimension usage.
- Effective Rank $\text{rank}_{\text{eff}}(\Sigma) = e^{\mathcal{H}_\Sigma}$: Scalar Indicator that measures compressibility or dimension reduction capacity.

- Angular Alignment $\cos \theta_{ij} = Q_i \cdot K_j$: Pseudo-metric that reflects semantic closeness in latent space.
- Selectivity Index $\mathcal{S}(A_i) = 1 - \frac{\sum_j A_{ij}^2}{(\sum_j A_{ij})^2}$: Statistical indicator that reflects the token-level sparsity and focus in attention matrix.
- Spectral Sparsity $\mathcal{P}(\Sigma) = \frac{|\{\sigma_i: |\sigma_i| < \epsilon\}|}{d_k}$: Structural indicator that indicates inactive latent directions and pruning potential.
- Perturbation Robustness $\Delta A = \|A(x) - A(x + \delta)\|_F$: Metric that quantifies behavioral consistency under small perturbations.

Algorithm 1 Integrating SVDA into a DPT Transformer encoder block (per forward pass)

Require: token embeddings $X \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times N \times d}$, number of heads h , head dimension $d_k = d/h$, projection weights W^Q, W^K, W^V, W^O , diagonal spectra $\Sigma_i = \text{diag}(\sigma_i)$

- 1: **for** $i = 1$ to h **do**
- 2: $Q_i \leftarrow XW_i^Q, K_i \leftarrow XW_i^K, V_i \leftarrow XW_i^V$ (linear projections)
- 3: $\tilde{Q}_i \leftarrow \text{normalize}(Q_i), \tilde{K}_i \leftarrow \text{normalize}(K_i)$ (row-wise ℓ_2 normalization)
- 4: $S_i \leftarrow \frac{(\tilde{Q}_i \Sigma_i) \tilde{K}_i^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ (SVDA scores)
- 5: $A_i \leftarrow \text{softmax}(S_i)$ (row-wise over keys)
- 6: $Z_i \leftarrow A_i V_i$ (head output)
- 7: **end for**
- 8: $Z \leftarrow \text{Concat}(Z_1, \dots, Z_h) W^O$ (multi-head output)
- 9: **return** Z

Figure 1. Operator-level view of the attention replacement used inside DPT encoder blocks: (a) conventional scaled dot-product attention [25], and (b) SVDA using diagonal spectral modulation via $Q\Sigma$ [8].

Experiments were conducted on the KITTI and NYU-v2 monocular depth estimation benchmarks. All RGB inputs were resized to 384×384 , and lightweight data augmentation was applied during training, including random horizontal flipping with probability 0.5, random cropping with probability 0.3, and random rotation with probability 0.2; no additional input normalization was used. For both datasets, the experimental protocol uses a train/validation/test split ratio of 60%/20%/20%. All models employed the same DPT-style backbone configuration, with embedding dimension 768, patch size 16, a ViT-style patch embedding pipeline, projection-based token readout, reassembly dimension 256, and a from-scratch Transformer implementation with 24 encoder layers. Training was performed from scratch in PyTorch for 100 epochs on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3080 GPU (CUDA 12.1, PyTorch 2.2.1), using the Adam optimizer with learning rate 3×10^{-4} . The batch size was set to 4 for KITTI and 2 for NYU-v2, and the total training time for the SVDA model was 78.8 hours on KITTI and 56.4 hours on NYU-v2. Depth supervision used a composite loss consisting of an L_1 reconstruction term, a scale-invariant logarithmic (SILog) term, and a gradient-consistency term, combined as $\mathcal{L}_{\text{depth}} = L_1 + 0.85 L_{\text{SILog}} + 0.15 L_{\text{grad}}$

over valid depth pixels. For SVDA runs, this task loss was further augmented with orthogonality regularization on the query/key projections. Baseline and SVDA variants were trained under the same protocol, with the only architectural difference being the replacement of standard dot-product attention with SVDA in the Transformer encoder blocks.

4. Results and Structural Indicators

Beyond accuracy and runtime, the evaluation examines interpretability and structural organization of attention via the SVDA indicators. Those indicators are computed for each head and layer at every epoch, enabling both temporal tracking and depth-wise analysis of attention dynamics. The empirical evaluation is conducted under a controlled setting in which the baseline DPT and the SVDA-enhanced variant share the same backbone, training protocol, and optimization setup, so that the effect of the attention reformulation can be examined directly.

Consistent convergence behavior is observed across KITTI and NYU-v2. As illustrated in Figure 2, validation losses are nearly identical between SVDA-enhanced and the baseline model, indicating stable optimization and no signs of overfitting. In addition, Tables 2 and 3 summarize the benchmark comparison results.

Figure 2. Validation loss over epochs for baseline and SVDA models across datasets. The models show nearly identical learning trajectories.

Table 2. Benchmark comparison on KITTI, evaluated at the checkpoint selected by validation AbsRel (lower is better). Selected epochs: Baseline = 65, SVDA = 66. Bold values indicate the better result for each metric; ties are shown in bold for both methods.

Method	AbsRel	SqRel	RMSE	RMSE _{log}	sRMSE _{log}	δ_1
Baseline	0.058	0.001	0.010	0.037	0.002	0.976
SVDA (ours)	0.056	0.001	0.011	0.035	0.002	0.979

Table 3. Benchmark comparison on NYU-v2, evaluated at the checkpoint selected by validation AbsRel (lower is better). Selected epochs: Baseline = 93, SVDA = 95. Bold values indicate the better result for each metric; ties are shown in bold for both methods.

Method	AbsRel	SqRel	RMSE	RMSE _{log}	sRMSE _{log}	δ_1
Baseline	0.133	0.010	0.079	0.093	0.013	0.865
SVDA (ours)	0.124	0.010	0.071	0.109	0.013	0.872

SVDA introduces only 0.01% additional parameters compared to the baseline, while increasing training time by approximately 13.6% on KITTI and 18.0% on NYU-v2, corresponding to an average overhead of 15.79%. In wall-clock terms, the total training time of

the SVDA model was approximately 3.7 days on KITTI and 2.4 days on NYU-v2, compared with 3.3 and 1.7 days for the corresponding baseline runs. This increase is consistent with the additional ℓ_2 -normalization, diagonal spectral modulation, and regularization operations introduced by SVDA. Part of this overhead is likely implementation-dependent and may be reduced in future through more optimized kernels or fused implementations of the additional normalization and spectral modulation steps. Given that the main contribution of the method lies in intrinsic interpretability and structured attention diagnostics, this trade-off remains acceptable in settings where transparency is an important requirement [26].

Temporal analysis of the interpretability indicators reported in Figures 3 and 4 reveals aspects of the internal workings of the Transformer architecture during training. Results show that spectral entropy and effective rank decrease steadily, signaling a reduction in the number of active latent directions. In parallel, spectral sparsity increases, indicating that uninformative spectral components are pruned. Angular alignment and the selectivity index exhibit minimal variation across epochs, suggesting that directional coherence and token-level focus are established early; perturbation robustness stabilizes quickly, implying that the model attains noise tolerance from the outset. These trends are clearly visible for both KITTI (Figure 3) and NYU-v2 (Figure 4), and they become observable only because SVDA was introduced into the Transformer architecture. The similarity of these patterns across datasets suggests that the core DPT architecture exhibits robust internal behavior. This observation is one of the benefits of using SVDA.

Furthermore, the per-layer distributions reveal a systematic depth-wise organization. Early layers retain higher entropy and rank, indicating broad spectral usage and diffuse attention, while deeper layers converge to low-rank, low-entropy profiles that emphasize a few dominant directions. Selectivity index increases with depth, showing that later layers route information more sharply across tokens, while early layers maintain distributed focus. Angular alignment is strongest in shallow layers and diminishes with depth. Perturbation robustness also increases in deeper layers, where attention becomes less sensitive to small input variations, thereby reinforcing stability near the decision stage. These results and conclusions would not be accessible in a fully opaque baseline architecture without introducing SVDA.

Taken together, these indicators admit a practical descriptive reading. Lower spectral entropy and effective rank indicate that attention is concentrated on fewer active latent directions, implying a more compact and selective internal organization. Higher spectral sparsity suggests that some spectral dimensions become effectively inactive, which facilitates inspection and may point to compactification potential. Stable angular alignment reflects a more consistent geometric organization of query–key relations, while higher selectivity in deeper layers indicates more focused routing of information. Increased perturbation robustness indicates that the attention mechanism remains stable under small input changes, which is desirable in settings where trust and operational reliability matter. Although descriptive rather than prescriptive, these quantities may in future work serve as diagnostic signals for model analysis and monitoring, and may support debugging, optimization, and deployment-related decisions.

Figure 3. SVDA interpretability diagnostics on KITTI. Each row corresponds to one indicator: (a) Spectral Entropy, (b) Effective Rank, (c) Angular Alignment, (d) Selectivity Index, (e) Spectral Sparsity, and (f) Perturbation Robustness. The first column shows evolution across training epochs and the second column shows the corresponding per-layer distribution (box plots).

Figure 4. SVDA interpretability diagnostics on NYU-v2. Each row corresponds to one indicator: (a) Spectral Entropy, (b) Effective Rank, (c) Angular Alignment, (d) Selectivity Index, (e) Spectral Sparsity, and (f) Perturbation Robustness. The first column shows evolution across training epochs and the second column shows the corresponding per-layer distribution (box plots).

5. Discussion

The integration of SVDA into monocular depth estimation does not alter predictive behavior in a substantial way. Instead, it reframes the task from asking whether accuracy improves, to asking how the underlying architecture organizes its representational capacity. The results show that SVDA maintains parity with the baseline while providing structured descriptions of spectral usage, directional alignment, and robustness. This descriptive role is the central contribution expected by SVDA. This study should therefore be read primarily as a controlled examination of how spectrally structured attention affects interpretability and internal organization in monocular depth estimation, rather than as an accuracy-oriented benchmarking campaign.

From this perspective, this paper showcases that SVDA serves as a diagnostic lens in monocular depth estimation. The observed reductions in entropy and rank, the rise of sparsity, and the layer-wise transitions reported are not prescriptive findings to be optimized toward, but descriptive patterns that reveal how the DPT backbone allocates attention across training and depth. Such patterns would remain opaque in conventional attention, where only dense, uninterpretable maps are available.

By shifting attention analysis into a spectral framework, SVDA aligns with broader efforts in explainable AI by making the organization of deep architectures observable without imposing external constraints or heuristic explanations. The importance of this shift is not in outperforming state-of-the-art metrics, but in providing a principled account of model dynamics that can be interrogated, compared across datasets, and eventually trusted in safety-critical applications.

Two natural directions for future work follow from the present study: scalability to larger backbones and higher-resolution regimes, and extension of the same descriptive analysis beyond monocular depth estimation to other dense prediction tasks.

This formulation is especially relevant in domains such as robotics, autonomous driving, and other safety-critical AI settings, where transparent internal behavior can support inspection and trust. By exposing structured descriptors of attention concentration, alignment, and robustness, SVDA provides a more interpretable account of how information is organized within the model.

In summary, the discussion does not concern accuracy gains, but transparency. SVDA describes, rather than prescribes, how attention behaves in monocular depth estimation, thus bridging its theoretical foundation with practical interpretability in vision Transformers.

6. Conclusions

This work applied SVD-Inspired Attention (SVDA) to the task of monocular depth estimation within a DPT framework. The results across KITTI and NYU-v2 confirm that SVDA preserves predictive accuracy while introducing a principled mechanism for examining the inner structure of attention. On KITTI, AbsRel improved from 0.058 to 0.056 and δ_1 from 0.976 to 0.979, while on NYU-v2, AbsRel improved from 0.133 to 0.124 and δ_1 from 0.865 to 0.872, with only 0.01% additional parameters and an average runtime overhead of 15.79%. Unlike methods that seek architectural improvements or performance gains, SVDA provides a descriptive account of how attention spectra evolve across training and depth, revealing compression, sparsity, alignment, and robustness that remain hidden in standard formulations.

The contribution of this study is therefore twofold: first, it demonstrates that SVDA can be integrated into dense prediction architectures while preserving competitive predictive performance; second, it shows that the resulting interpretability indicators enable system-

atic and intrinsic inspection of representational dynamics. In doing so, SVDA transforms attention from an opaque mechanism into a structured and quantifiable process.

Future work will extend this descriptive perspective to other dense prediction tasks, investigate integration with lighter model variants, and examine how the same spectral framework behaves at larger model scales.

By grounding explanations in spectral analysis rather than heuristic visualization, SVDA offers a pathway toward attention models that can be not only accurate, but also meaningfully understood.

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